
SUPPORTING THE RESEARCH WORK OF AN H2020 CYBERSECURITY PROJECT WITH INNOVATION MANAGEMENT TOOLS AND METHODOLOGY - A CASE STUDY OF THE ECHO PROJECT

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Abstract

The European Union provides structured funding to solve priority problems affecting the Union as a whole and the individual Member States, including open calls for tenders. Problems are regularly evaluated, reviewed, and supplemented. The projects submitted to the calls are carefully selected based on a transparent, strict criteria system. Project ideas usually come from a small initiating team, and the consortium undertaking the implementation is built around this. During the implementation of individual projects, the work takes place according to a well-defined work plan, the progress of which is constantly monitored by the Commission. With all of this, even in the case of completed projects, it is difficult to verify whether the original intention of novelty and innovation content was realised and whether the project produced a useful result reflecting the original problem. This article presents the process and methodology of good practice for a specific cybersecurity project. With the involvement of project members, the problem statement, solution, and response can be validated on a much wider scale than usual, making it much more likely to deliver a useful, relevant solution for the community during and after the project's life cycle. It is presented how the Innovation Management work package of the ECHO (European Network of Cybersecurity Centers and Competence Hub for Innovation and Operations) H2020 research and development project mobilised the members of the other professional work packages, and along which activities it was possible to achieve that the problem definition became more precise, and thus in the development process it was possible to rely on this definition continuously and to check the expected results and effects.

It can be determined based on the good practice described in the article that the practical application of the innovation methodology, and thus the joint thinking of experts, developers, and cyber defence specialists working in different fields and putting it into a structured form, resulted in timely and exact response to a shock (Covid) and the project could publish a relevant white paper about the new cyber threats arising from the pandemic. Those results were then built into the development process, and the products were adjusted accordingly, which supported the high quality and future usefulness of the project's deliverables and products.

Keywords

Cybersecurity, Innovation management, Exploitation, Research and development, Good practice

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1 Introduction

The European Union provides structured funding to solve priority problems affecting the Union as a whole and the individual Member States, including open calls for grants and tenders. Problems are regularly evaluated, reviewed, and supplemented. The projects submitted to the calls are carefully selected based on a transparent, strict criteria system. Project ideas usually come from a small initiating team, and the consortium undertaking the implementation is built around this. During the implementation of individual projects, the work takes place according to a well-defined work plan, the progress of which is constantly monitored by the Commission. Even in the case of completed projects, verifying whether the original intention of novelty and innovation content was realised and whether the project produced a useful result reflecting the original problem is difficult. Within this rigid structure, it is also almost impossible to reflect on the changing of the original societal/market need during the project's lifetime.

The article presents the process and methodology of good practice of a specific project, where the problem statement and the solution can be validated with the involvement of project members, enabling the delivery of relevant solutions for the EU after finishing the project.

It presented how the Innovation Management work package of the ECHO (European Network of Cybersecurity Centres and Competence Hub for Innovation and Operations) H2020 R&D project mobilised the members of the other professional work packages.

The innovation management (Walder, 2021) activities presented in the article made it possible to achieve a more precise problem definition, which allowed the development process to rely on it continuously and check the expected results and effects against it.

It can be established that the practical application of the innovation methodology, resulting in the joint thinking of experts, developers, and cyber defence specialists, supported the high quality and future usefulness of the project's deliverables and products.

2 Cybersecurity projects in the EU

One of the major challenges of the EU is to strengthen its cybersecurity capacity and capabilities. The purpose of a European Cybersecurity Network and Competence Centre - delivered through 4 key pilot projects (CONCORDIA, ECHO, SPARTA, and CyberSec4Europe (Figure 1) aimed to retain and develop cybersecurity technological and industrial capacities and strengthen and sustain Europe's cybersecurity competence. Each of the four projects took a different approach to these goals. The four projects coordinated their activities and worked together with other European cybersecurity actors to advance cybersecurity research in Europe. The range of cybersecurity-related activities included demonstration use cases in eHealth, finance, telecommunications, smart cities, and transportation.

Figure 1 - H2020 pilot projects

Source: EC infographics

These pilot projects had over 160 partners, including major companies, SMEs, universities, and cybersecurity research institutes from 26 EU Member States. The overall EU investment in these projects was over 63.5 million Euros. The four pilots were selected among 12 eligible proposals that the European Commission has received for the Horizon 2020 call SU-ICT-032018. This call was part of the Horizon 2020 focus area 'Boosting the effectiveness of the Security Union (SU)'.

3 Research problem

Based on their previous experience in the field of European research projects, the authors state that the research and development work during the projects' lifetimes is not optimal. Innovation-based methodologies embedded into the project workflow can improve the cooperation and information sharing of the project partners and the validation and outcome of project results.

This statement applies to all the project cases where the environment and market needs and circumstances change during the project's lifetime, requiring adjustments to be made to the deliverables. But the problem is even bigger when unexpected, sudden events dramatically change the landscape (pandemics, financial crisis, war, political turmoil) (Zupancic, 2023), and the project must make a swift evaluation of the situation and implement the necessary adjustments and increase organisational resilience (Liu, 2021).

The following use case depicts this process, how the new cyber threats caused by the Covid pandemic could be detected and summarised rapidly using the innovation management methodologies (Jobbágy, 2021), how it supported the development work of the project internally, and how it supported all the EU community by publishing the findings in a White Paper.

4 The ECHO use case

ECHO (the European network of Cybersecurity centers and competence Hub for innovation and Operations) was one of the four projects to connect and share knowledge across multiple domains to develop a common cybersecurity strategy for Europe.

Figure 2 - ECHO main products

Source: ECHO project presentation, Matteo Merialdo et al.

The work was divided into six different but connected main activities, as shown in Figure 2. Federated Cyber Ranges (FCR) and Early Warning Systems (EWS) aimed to prepare for cyber threats and share knowledge timely and effectively between EU cyber actors (Carvalho, 2019). The three frameworks – Cyberskills, Certification, and Multi Sector Assessment – produced frameworks and benchmarks for future cooperation. Ultimately the Governance Model provided an operational structure where the coordinated knowledge sharing of partners on cybersecurity development can be continuously conducted even after the project's finish.

The final governance structure has been established after a long negotiation process, as shown in Figure 3. The transition from the ECHO project life to future independent operations was only possible by introducing a central hub, where all the project results would be deposited, and the public and private utilisation could be monitored and separated.

Figure 4 shows the planned working structure of the ECHO project, submitted during the time of application. It is a clear and logical breakdown of the working plan. The main development work packages (WP2-3-4-5-6) are followed by prototyping and demonstration work (WP7-8) and it is framed by the usual coordination and project management (WP1) and Dissemination (WP9) activities. It is interesting to realise that already at the project planning, WP9 aimed to deliver much more than the usual communication and dissemination work, covering exploitation, innovation management, and societal aspects. As will be elaborated later in this article, this forward-looking planning was vital for the project's success.

Figure 3 - ECHO governance model

Source: ECHO project presentation, Todor Tagarev et al.

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Figure 4 shows the planned working structure of the ECHO project, submitted during the time of application. It is a clear and logical breakdown of the working plan. The main development work packages (WP2-3-4-5-6) are followed by prototyping and demonstration work (WP7-8) and it is framed by the usual coordination and project management (WP1) and Dissemination (WP9) activities. It is interesting to realise that already at the project planning, WP9 aimed to deliver much more than the usual communication and dissemination work, covering exploitation, innovation management, and societal aspects. As will be elaborated later in this article, this forward-looking planning was vital for the project's success.

Figure 4 - planned working structure

Source: ECHO project presentation, Matteo Merialdo et al.

Figure 5 shows the actual representation of project work and especially the interdependencies and knowledge transfer relations between the work packages on the task level. It is worth noticing how knowledge flows between different development stages and how the information from development tasks was fed into prototyping and demonstration cases. The importance of governance (the work defining the future operational model) and exploitation (market needs, business modelling) is much more visible from the multiple direct connections to the development work.

Figure 5 - actual working structure

Source: ECHO project presentation, Matteo Merialdo et al.

4.1 Role of WP9

Usually, EU project partners consider the communication and dissemination work as a must and nuisance (it is compulsory) as it is viewed by many as taking away resources from the development and professional work. As exploitation is already a mandatory activity, too, it brought in further complications for the development work packages – as the project must continuously investigate the need and added value of the products/services created during the lifetime of the project and their commercial or societal value and impact.

Figure 6 - WP9 task structure

Source: ECHO project presentation, Márton Kis et al.

As Figure 6 depicts, ECHO took this important approach even one step further. WP9 did not just deliver the regular dissemination work by publishing the project results on different online channels and international conferences or publications. The work was carefully planned, and with exploitation as the main focus, one additional winning element was added. Innovation management work became part of WP9 activities. While TRL levels and evolution were monitored carefully, the biggest advantage lay in introducing the structured co-creation activities (Ideathons and Hackathons), where the consortium contributed to predefined problems and their solutions. As detailed in later chapters, these innovation management tools enabled the teams to better express the actual underlying problems (by codifying problem statements), and it was also part of the co-creation process to search for solutions for those problems and carry out a joint validation process.

4.2 Challenges during the project

Figure 7 includes the 5 main challenges of the project that could be identified. As the work started in 2019, the planned routine started to function – a usual and effective combination of in-person and virtual meetings. This has been abruptly changed with the introduction of travel bans in the entire EU. Project partners had to reorganise work to only virtual. During the process, a lot of problems were identified. Thus, the partners decided to focus the innovation management activities on clarifying the exact problems, cyber threats, and potential solutions – which led to organising an all-project hackathon and resulted in the published unique white paper discussed in detail in a later chapter.

Figure 7 - ECHO challenges

Source: own figure

The complicated work structure posed a threat in itself, but combined with COVID-19, it became obvious that the WP1 coordination team must put in extra effort to streamline the information flow within and between work packages to avoid major delays and quality decreases in project deliverables and results. Extra management focus paid off, the project partners adjusted to the new normal, and the full virtual work could deliver the required quality.

The size of the project meant, that the 30+ partners' and 200+ individual contributors' work had to be coordinated. The EU projects usually carry some cultural differences between the different member states, which is expected. The cooperation problems from different academic and private companies' approaches are also known. Further complications derived from the different mindsets of developers, hackers, engineers, academics, and politicians.

The last two challenges are interconnected – it is difficult to define the current cybersecurity challenges of Europe, let alone describe in detail what those problems will be in 5 or 25 years. The project work has been conducted following a preset path and work plan. The developers had no time neither focus on following the long-term or rapid short-term changes and shocks affecting their work, ultimately resulting in the need to make major adjustments to the planned products and services as cybersecurity threats and challenges might have changed drastically or the future need might be different from what the project anticipated at the proposal phase. These open questions were articulated into problem statements and fed into the co-creation events to stimulate discussion, exchange of views, and ultimately arrive at new ideas, results, and change of plans.

4.3 Innovation Management in Action

The innovation management approach was an organic part of the project's development process from the very start, as visualised in Figure 8 below. As the project's development work moved forward from the initial goal setting through setting roadmaps, launching prototypes, defining the targeted governance structure, and piloting asset demonstration cases, ultimately reaching market-ready results, innovation management activities were embedded in the process.

Figure 8 - Innovation management methodology

Source: ECHO project presentation, Marton Kis et al.

Regular Ideaathon events were organised, and development WPs were directly involved. The Ideaathon results were used in research and development work to support sustainability and exploitation planning. The events always started with a high-level problem definition. This was then further refined to exact problem statements and subject to group validation during the events.

Once there was an agreement on the exact challenge, problem, or obstacle, the co-creation could commence, aiming to find the best solution. The events always concluded with a list of proposed solutions and actionable items to be directly used in the development process, and some of the public interest was published as blog items or white papers for wider uptake.

5 Identified cyber threats during Covid

Using the above methodology, the ECHO project partners could identify the changing environment during COVID-19 and capture the new or increased cyber threats arising from the abruptly changing digital working environment of major populations worldwide.

This unique approach also enabled ECHO to synthesise the project findings and publish a white paper very quickly after the onset of the pandemic, helping not only the project work but the whole EU community to raise awareness and take precautions against the new cyber threats. ECHO efforts became a major part of the coordinated EC efforts to step up against adverse COVID-related cybersecurity issues.

The following is the summary of the findings published in the white paper (ECHO, 2020).

5.1 General considerations

The white paper established that the general conclusion is that during Covid, the approaches and the technology being used by hackers were the same as it was before. However, there were two major differences. Firstly, the transition to online working and schooling.

Secondly, the human factor is an even bigger weakness than before because of the instability arising from limited information and increased fears of the pandemic, thus becoming more vulnerable and less suspicious to cyber attacks.

5.2 Profile of the Attacker

Three profiles of potential threat actors are identified: the criminal hacker, the hacktivist, and the nation-state-supported hacker's group.

5.3 Modus operandi of attack

During the event, several attack vectors were discussed in combination with the different profiles of the attackers, as summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 - Modus operandi of attack

Platforms	Attack method/threat	Scenarios
Emails	open the attachment, download the file, click the link	WHO, donation, conspiracy, home delivery
SMS	cloned websites of authorities	government announcement
Messaging apps	cloned websites	fake news
BYOD	use of home PC vulnerability, office apps installations	
Critical infra providers	rapid change from stand-alone to remote access	
Medical devices	malware threat	
Covid applications	steal of personal information	
Online conf apps	cloned websites calling for online meetings	

Source: own table

6 Conclusion

Cybersecurity is one of the major challenges for several reasons (pandemics, wars, digitalisation) for the European Union. EU R&D projects are useful and efficient in delivering results to tackle this issue and bring fresh, innovative, and coordinated solutions. However, these projects are not ideal for delivering timely results; actual needs and goals have to be updated, and they will change during the lifetime of a project. Problems arise from the difficulties of working in diverse, multi-national, and multi-disciplinary teams, offline and online. The EC valuation of preset milestones and deliverables does not leave enough space to adjust results to tackle new needs and challenges.

Coordinated innovation management (IM) activities can be vital in facing these challenges. From identifying and validating the key demand/market need to validating results, IM can support several important steps of a project's development process. Continuous cooperation and co-creation among project members will lead to useful results.

ECHO partners and individual project members pioneered this approach, embedding the IM methodologies into the daily routine of the project work across the whole project timeline. This resulted in better information flow, common definitions, and an understanding of the previously listed challenges. The common ground then helped the developers and professional members within the project make the necessary adjustments to the products so that they could be applied to the changing needs of the cybersecurity landscape.

The research should continue to analyse the methodology used in the ECHO project to evaluate how to standardise it and how it can be used as good practice in future Horizon projects.

Resources

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